

Biofacies of Abundant Foraminifera in Relation to Bottom Sediments in Outer Channel of Chilka Lake, Odisha, East Coast of India

Anil Kumar, A. Pallavi, Ch. Ravisekhar, P. Ganapathi Rao and R. Kaladhar*

Department of Geology, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam - 530 003, India

*E-mail: profkaladhar@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The Chilka Lake is a brackish water lagoon and is located between 19°25' and 19°54'N and 85°6' and 85°38'E along the East Coast of India. Based on the physical and chemical parameters, the Lake is divided into four zones, viz., the Southern, Central and Northern Sectors and the Outer Channel area (Fig.1). The 32km long Outer Channel connects with the Bay of Bengal at Arakudha and Satpada villages and forms a typical estuarine environment. Sediment and water samples were collected from fifteen stations from the Outer Channel in each season i.e. in May and December, 2009 for faunal studies and determination of sediment character and for water analysis. The salinity ranges from 30.8‰ to 40.9‰, temperature varies from 23.6°C to 31.5°C, dissolved oxygen varies from 3.8ml/l to 7.2ml/l and hydrogen ion concentration ranges from 6.9 to 8.1. Sand dominates the other types of substrate towards the mouth of the Channel at Arakudha village. Organic matter content of the sediment varies from 0.31% to 2.0%. Thirteen abundant Foraminiferal species have been identified from the Outer Channel among which *Asterorotalia inflata*, *A. trispinosa*, *Cibicides lobatulus*, *Nonion grateloupi* and *Pararotalia nipponica* are considered as stenohaline marine species and the other eight species viz., *Ammobaculites exiguus*, *Miliammina fusca*, *M. fusca* var., *Quinqueloculina seminulum*, *Ammonia beccarii*, *A. tepida*, *Elphidium craticulatum* and *Nonion depressulus* are considered as species endemic to the Outer Channel. The endemic species could tolerate higher temperatures and salinities and occur more or less in equal proportions in the Channel. The biofacies of the Outer Channel are named after the eight endemic species. These are considered as typical biofacies of an estuarine environment and can serve as tools for the delineation of the paleoenvironments.

Keywords: Chilka Lake, Foraminifera, Stenohaline, Endemic, Biofacies, Organic Matter

INTRODUCTION

The Chilka Lake is a brackish water lagoon, spreading over the Puri, Khurda and Ganjam Districts of the Odisha State on the east coast of India. The western and eastern margins of the lake are fringed by the Eastern Ghat hill range (Tripathy, 2007-11). It is the largest coastal lagoon (1165 km²) in India and the second largest in the

world and is located between 19°25' and 19°54'N and 85°6' and 85°38'E (Fig.1). A 60 km long barrier beach called Rejhansa (Singh *et al.*, 2005) is formed by northerly currents in the Bay of Bengal and resulted in the formation of this lake and forms its eastern side. Several inland rivers such as Bhargavi, Daya, Makara, Malguni and Nuna Rivers, carry freshwater and silt into the lake. It is estimated that 13 million tons of silt is brought annually into the lake by rivers and rivulets that drain into it (Chilka Lake Development Authority, 2008).

The depth of the lake varies from 0.3 m in the dry season to 1.8 m to 4.2 m in the rainy season. Based on the physical and chemical parameters, the lake is divided into four zones, viz., the Southern, Central and Northern Sectors and the Outer Channel. The 32km long Outer Channel connects the lake with the Bay of Bengal at Arakudha village (forming the old mouth) and at Satpada village (forming the new mouth). Sea water enters into the Outer Channel through the old and new mouths and thus forms a typical estuarine environment.

METHODOLOGY

Sediment samples for Foraminiferal faunal studies, sediment texture analysis and determination of organic matter content and water samples for the determination of salinity and dissolved oxygen content were collected from fifteen stations (Fig.2) in each season, i.e., in May and December 2009 (Pre-monsoon and Post-monsoon seasons) from the Outer Channel. Temperature and hydrogen-ion concentration were measured at all the fifteen stations. Living Foraminifera and sediment and water characteristics were determined following standard methods (living fauna: Walton, 1952; sediment texture: Carver, 1971 and Folk, 1954; organic matter: Sverdrup *et al.*, 1942; salinity and dissolved oxygen: Strickland and Parsons, 1968).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bottom Water Characteristics

Salinity of the water collected from each station was calculated using salinometer. During the observation

Fig.1. Location map of the Chilika Lake

period bottom water salinity is in the range from 35.0‰ to 40.9‰ in May and from 30.8‰ to 33.3‰ in December. Difference in salinity between May and December is of the order of 5‰ to 7‰ (Table 1). The temperatures of the bottom waters were measured immersing a thermometer into the waters immediately after collection using water sampler. Bottom water temperature has a range from 29.0°C to 31.5°C in May and from 23.6°C to 25.6°C in December (Table 1). The dissolved oxygen was determined applying Winkler's

chemical method (Strickland and Parson, 1968). Dissolved oxygen content varies from 3.8 ml/l to 4.8 ml/l in May and from 3.9 ml/l to 7.2 ml/l in December in the Outer Channel. Greater water circulation and presence of some phytoplanktons obviously result in higher concentration of dissolved oxygen (Table 1). pH of the bottom waters was measured using portable pH meter after collection of bottom water samples. pH ranges from 6.9 to 7.8 and from 7.0 to 8.1 in May and December respectively (Table 1).

Fig.2. Map showing location of stations in the Outer Channel, Chilika Lake

Table 1: Ecological variables and sediment characteristics of the Outer Channel, Chilka Lake

Station Numbers	Salinity(‰)		Temp.(°C)		Dissolved oxygen(ml/l)		pH		Sediment type	Organic matter(%)	
	May	Dec	May	Dec	May	Dec	May	Dec		May & Dec	May
	1	35.1	30.9	29.5	23.8	4.1	6.4	7.6	7.7	Sand	0.3
2	35.0	30.8	29	23.8	4.0	6.3	7.5	7.7	Sand	0.3	0.4
3	37.0	31.0	30.5	23.6	4.1	4.2	7.2	7.3	Sand	0.3	0.4
4	38.0	30.8	29.5	23.6	4.2	4.4	7.1	7.4	Sand	0.3	0.4
5	39.0	31.2	30	23.9	3.8	3.9	7.2	7.9	Sand	0.3	0.4
6	38.0	31.1	30	24.0	3.9	4.0	7.8	8.0	Silty sand	0.3	0.4
7	38.1	31.2	30	24.1	4.8	6.3	7.6	7.8	Muddy sand	0.4	1.0
8	38.2	31.3	30	24.2	4.1	6.4	7.7	7.9	Clayey sand	0.4	0.9
9	39.8	32.1	30	24.0	4.2	6.9	7.3	7.4	Clayey sand	0.9	1.1
10	39.0	32.0	30	24.1	4.5	7.0	7.1	7.3	Clayey sand	1.0	1.1
11	40.9	33.3	30	24.6	3.9	6.1	7.0	7.1	Clayey sand	1.2	1.9
12	40.8	33.2	30.5	24.5	3.9	6.2	6.9	7.0	Clayey sand	1.3	1.4
13	36.0	30.8	30.5	24.9	4.2	7.1	7.6	7.9	Clayey sand	1.4	2.0
14	36.1	30.9	30.5	25.0	4.3	7.2	7.8	8.1	Clayey sand	1.4	1.9
15	36.2	30.8	31.5	25.6	3.8	6.9	7.2	7.5	Sandy clay	1.3	1.3

Bottom Sediment Characteristics and Organic Matter Content

The sediment texture analysis was done applying Krumbein and Pettijohn (1938) method. Sand dominates the other types of substrate towards the mouth at Arakudha village and clayey sand towards the southern part of the Outer Channel. Organic matter of the sediment was calculated by chemical and titration method (Sverdrup *et al.*, 1942). Organic matter content of sediment ranges from 0.31% to 1.4% in May and from 0.4% to 2.0% in December. Sand is poor and sandy clay and clayey sand are rich in organic matter content especially in December.

Biofacies of the Abundant Foraminifera

The relative occurrence of the abundant species in the Outer Channel of the Chilka Lake are represented in Fig.3. Thirteen Foraminiferal species have occurred abundantly in the Outer Channel of the Chilka Lake (Fig. 4). Among them *Asterorotalia inflata*, *A. trispinosa*, *Cibicides lobatulus*, *Nonion grateloupi* and *Pararotalia nipponica* are considered as stenohaline marine species and *Ammobaculites exiguus*, *Miliammina fusca*, *M. fusca* var., *Quinqueloculina seminulum*, *Ammonia beccarii*, *A. tepida*, *Elphidium craticulatum* and *Nonion depressulus* are considered as endemic to the Outer Channel.

Fig. 3. Relative abundances of Stenohaline forms, forms endemic to the lake and forms common to scarce occurrence in the Outer Channel

Fig. 4. Species of Foraminifera from the Outer Channel of Chilka Lake. **a)** *Asterorotalia inflata* spiral side view, **b)** *Asterorotalia inflata* umbilical side view, **c)** *A. trispinosa* dorsal view **d)** *A. trispinosa* ventral view, **e)** *Cibicides lobatulus* (General view), **f)** *Nonion grateloupi* (General view), **g)** *Pararotalia nipponica* umbilical side view, **h)** *Pararotalia nipponica* spiral side view, **i)** *Ammobaculites exiguus* (General view), **j)** *Miliammina fusca* four chamber side view, **k)** *Miliammina fusca* three chamber side view, **l)** *M. fusca* var. (General view), **m)** *Quinqueloculina seminulum* four chamber side view, **n)** *Quinqueloculina seminulum* three chamber side view, **o)** *Ammonia beccarii* spiral side view, **p)** *Ammonia beccarii* umbilical side view, **q)** *A. tepida* oblique, **r)** *A. tepida* spiral side view, **s)** *Elphidium craticulatum* (General view), **t)** *Nonion depressulus* general view, **u)** *Nonion depressulus* apertural view.

Biofacies of the Stenohaline Species

Brief remarks concerning occurrence and distribution of the five stenohaline species are given in Table 2. In general, individually these species do not appear to be significant. Therefore, their, combined population sizes and relative abundances are considered (Table 1 and Fig.3) to evaluate their significance in the waters of the Outer Channel in the Chilka Lake.

Biofacies of the Endemic Species

Eight endemic species of Foraminifera are recognized in the Outer Channel and the biofacies are represented on their names as *Ammonia beccarii* biofacies, *A. tepida* biofacies, *Miliammina fusca* biofacies, *Miliammina fusca* var. biofacies, *Ammobaculites exiguus* biofacies, *Quinqueloculina seminulum* biofacies, *Nonion depressulus* biofacies and *Elphidium craticulatum*

Table 2: Absolute and relative abundances of populations of stenohaline marine Foraminifera of abundant occurrence in the Outer Channel, Chilka Lake.

Station Numbers	Absolute size (Number of specimens/12.5ml wet sediment)				*Relative abundance (%)			
	Living populations		Total populations		Living populations		Total population	
	May 2009	Dec 2009	May 2009	Dec 2009	May 2009	Dec 2009	May 2009	Dec 2009
1	-	2	21	29	-	11.8	15.0	20.0
2	5	4	32	33	33.3	19.0	17.6	18.9
3	4	4	46	48	25.0	10.0	19.0	22.2
4	10	14	54	61	11.1	14.3	13.0	17.2
5	12	20	56	43	10.4	16.8	12.2	9.1
6	16	20	71	65	15.6	15.4	12.6	12.2
7	10	21	72	93	8.0	15.3	11.6	14.7
8	4	8	67	71	5.3	11.1	12.8	12.9
9	5	17	67	91	5.0	15.5	11.7	14.5
10	5	16	80	103	5.6	12.2	11.6	12.8
11	8	11	77	79	10.7	9.5	10.1	9.2
12	6	9	80	74	5.8	7.8	8.8	8.1
13	8	6	103	86	9.0	5.4	10.2	8.1
14	12	10	103	65	13.8	7.5	10.8	6.5
15	13	11	87	83	13.7	9.6	9.8	7.6

* The relative abundance are calculated considering the 13 abundant species.

Table 3: Occurrence of living and total (living + dead) populations of endemic species in the Outer Channel, Chilka Lake.

Station Numbers	Absolute size (Number of specimens/12.5ml wet sediment)				Station Numbers	Absolute size (Number of specimens/12.5ml wet sediment)			
	Living populations		Total populations			Living populations		Total populations	
	May 2009	Dec 2009	May 2009	Dec 2009		May 2009	Dec 2009	May 2009	Dec 2009
<i>Ammonia beccarii</i> (Linne)					<i>Miliammina fusca</i> var (Brady)				
1	2	6	25	32	1	-	-	-	-
2	-	2	16	21	2	-	-	14	-
3	4	8	45	36	3	1	2	16	21
4	16	10	48	52	4	14	17	40	38
5	12	18	52	68	5	17	10	58	52
6	5	21	61	72	6	2	12	31	48
7	21	32	82	95	7	3	5	25	29
8	1	13	22	52	8	-	2	12	32
9	7	12	31	39	9	12	4	29	22
10	18	21	72	85	10	3	8	16	39
11	11	16	120	130	11	1	3	12	16
12	21	31	150	120	12	5	8	16	21
13	17	15	161	172	13	7	10	42	52
14	13	20	140	167	14	5	16	35	60
15	21	35	160	190	15	9	7	31	42
<i>Ammonia tepida</i> (Cushman)					<i>Ammabaculites exiguus</i> (Cushman and Bronniman)				
1	2	2	21	15	1	-	-	10	6
2	2	8	31	42	2	-	1	20	16
3	-	7	16	23	3	2	3	48	32
4	5	11	30	42	4	14	7	120	48
5	10	15	62	72	5	-	10	28	32
6	16	9	85	52	6	8	3	42	28
7	20	19	92	120	7	20	12	82	62
8	-	7	15	96	8	15	11	103	75
9	9	16	25	117	9	11	9	160	102
10	21	22	120	130	10	-	3	75	48
11	17	6	112	118	11	4	14	89	79
12	16	13	120	98	12	8	6	104	98
13	12	18	132	140	13	6	10	130	120
14	14	20	150	160	14	10	16	162	110
15	19	10	140	152	15	5	13	120	152

Table 3: Contd.

Station Numbers	Absolute size (Number of specimens/12.5ml wet sediment)			
	Living populations		Total populations	
	May 2009	Dec 2009	May 2009	Dec 2009
<i>Miliammina fusca</i> (Brady)				
1	-	2	14	16
2	-	1	20	12
3	2	7	19	12
4	20	22	48	45
5	31	16	62	72
6	25	26	58	82
7	10	3	42	16
8	21	12	68	38
9	32	20	104	84
10	-	16	47	92
11	9	19	36	102
12	18	14	132	146
13	16	22	140	160
14	12	20	120	130
15	22	15	160	158
<i>Nonion depressulus</i> (Walker and Jacob)				
1	-	1	3	7
2	-	-	7	2
3	2	4	15	10
4	1	-	20	8
5	3	6	40	28
6	6	10	45	39
7	15	12	36	40
8	9	3	26	32
9	12	14	48	56
10	15	20	80	102
11	10	24	96	126
12	7	19	76	98
13	10	12	81	61
14	8	10	90	72
15	6	7	20	80

Station Numbers	Absolute size (Number of specimens/12.5ml wet sediment)			
	Living populations		Total populations	
	May 2009	Dec 2009	May 2009	Dec 2009
<i>Quinqueloculina seminulum</i> (Linne)				
1	3	2	41	32
2	6	3	32	40
3	-	2	21	16
4	10	16	48	52
5	16	20	86	82
6	20	22	150	120
7	19	27	160	145
8	22	9	180	121
9	11	15	86	96
10	25	19	170	180
11	14	21	180	176
12	21	11	201	216
13	1	16	192	230
14	9	17	120	194
15	14	23	130	206
<i>Elphidium craticulatum</i> (Fichtel and Moll)				
1	-	2	6	8
2	2	2	10	9
3	1	3	15	18
4	-	1	7	9
5	4	4	16	20
6	5	7	22	25
7	7	6	31	28
8	4	7	32	35
9	1	3	24	22
10	3	6	29	38
11	1	2	41	43
12	2	4	30	38
13	3	3	35	42
14	4	4	38	35
15	2	4	22	25

biofacies. The biofacies are represented in Fig.3

The biofacies of all the eight endemic species are supported by the salinity ranging from 30.8‰ in December to 40.9‰ in May, temperature ranging from 23.6°C in December to 31.5°C in May, dissolved oxygen ranging from 3.8ml/l in May to 7.2ml/l in December and hydrogen ion concentration ranging from 6.9 in May to 8.1 in December.

All the eight endemic species could withstand higher salinities and higher temperatures. Dissolved oxygen increases slightly towards the southern end of the Channel and supports higher populations of the endemic species. pH is more or less the same throughout the Channel and has little effect on the abundant occurrence of the species.

The substrate of the Outer Channel is represented by sand, silty sand, muddy sand, clayey sand and sandy clay. Sand dominates the other types of substrate towards the old mouth at Arakudha village and clayey sand towards the northern part of the Outer Channel. The organic matter content of the sediment ranges from 0.31% in May to 2.0% in December. Sand is poor and sandy clay and

clayey sand is rich in organic matter content. Sandy clay supports the occurrence of all the eight biofacies of the endemic species of Foraminifera perhaps due to being rich in organic matter content.

A correlation of standing crops of the eight endemic species with ecological factors shows that they can tolerate temperatures of 23.6°C to 31.5°C and salinities of 30.8‰ to 40.9‰. However, their active reproduction normally takes place at a range of temperatures 27°C to 33°C and salinity 30.0‰ to 40.0‰ and dissolved oxygen 3.0ml/l to 7ml/l. Hence, these eight endemic species and their biofacies can be considered as representatives of an estuarine environment and can serve as tools for the delineation of estuarine paleoenvironments.

CONCLUSIONS

Chilka Lake is a brackish water lagoon. Based on the physical and chemical parameters, the lake is divided into the Southern, Central and Northern Sectors and the Outer Channel. Sediment and water samples were collected

from fifteen stations from the Outer Channel for faunal and ecological studies. Thirteen species of Foraminifera are of abundant occurrence of which *Ammonia beccarii*, *A. tepida*, *Miliammina fusca*, *Miliammina fusca* var., *Ammobaculites exiguus*, *Quinqueloculina seminulum*, *Nonion depressulus* and *Elphidium craticulatum* are considered as species endemic to the Outer Channel and the biofacies of the Outer Channel are described on their names. These eight biofacies occur in more or less equal proportions in the Outer Channel and are represented by higher temperatures and salinities, clayey

sand and higher percentages of organic matter content. These eight species and their biofacies can be considered as representatives of an estuarine environment. The other five abundant species viz., *Asterorotalia inflata*, *A. trispinosa*, *Cibicides lobatulus*, *Nonion grateloupi* and *Pararotalia nipponica* are considered as stenohaline marine species which do not appear to be significant. Hence, their combined population sizes and relative abundances are considered to evaluate their significance in the Outer Channel of the Chilka Lake.

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